

TIME MANAGEMENT IN A MODERN KINDERGARTEN INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: Reforming preschool education within the framework of the modern system of continuous education is a reality at the level of state policy. Based on this, the meaningful use of kindergarten time technology, its management increases the efficiency of the educational process in preschool educational organizations, leads to the early development of the mental and physical side of children. This increases the efficiency of preschool education. The article analyzes the scientific and theoretical aspects of these issues.

Keywords: Psychologist, preschool educational organization, director, stress, technology, time, time management.

Psychological changes occur in the mind of the leader and are determined by the readiness to introduce innovations and change the style of leadership. A modern leader should understand that the philosophy of influence in education management has been replaced by the philosophy of interaction and cooperation based on the principles of humanization and democratization. The purpose of the management is the development and self-development of teachers, pedagogical conditions for the realization of their potential, in order to achieve high realistic standards, rating indicators and competitiveness among other kindergartens in the city. is to create.

MTT directors are familiar with the concept of working in an emergency system, where a large volume of work needs to be completed in a short time, with high quality and efficiency.

Working in "stress" mode leads to emotional exhaustion for teachers, which cannot affect the achievement of long-term goals.

Therefore, managers have a very tough task to use their working time wisely - they need to plan not only their time, but also the working time of their subordinates.

Functional changes are determined by the expansion of the range of management functions. Prognostic, political-diplomatic, managerial are added to the classics, which include four main factors:

- determination of relevant theoretically based and practical goals and objectives;

- strategic planning of activities of all participants of the preschool education process;
- selection and implementation of established priority goals, correction of previously selected tactics and vector of activity in accordance with real (changed) conditions;
- competent self-analysis of management activities, control of the success of the development of the institution, analysis of the activities of all participants of the educational process.

Changes in methodological approaches to the management of preschool educational organization are relevant for kindergarten. We see the solution to this problem in the search for original mechanisms and the use of technologies aimed at increasing the efficiency of the institution.

It was no accident that we turned to time management technology.

Analyzing the main aspects, we focused on several important conclusions made by the leaders of preschool education organizations that have adopted this technology in practice:

1) the faster the preschool education organization develops, the greater the burden will be on all specialists of all departments or on each member of the team, therefore there is a need to introduce time management technologies into the management activities of the leader;

2) the use of technology makes it possible to achieve a high level of fulfillment of annual tasks (up to 99%) based on the precise division of tasks of each educator or creative groups, which guarantees an increase in labor efficiency;

3) during the introduction of technology, a positive psychological environment is established in the team, readiness for innovation is formed through high efficiency and creative initiative.

For a long time, many educational managers were skeptical about time management. This technology is not only developed and used in the economic sphere, but its effectiveness in other spheres is highly appreciated. Most academic papers, literary articles and manuals are related to business management, business planning, economic structure or network expansion. Therefore, this technology seems to be only economic.

At first glance, it may seem uninteresting, even meaningless, but the practical value of this technology can be assessed only by obtaining specific positive, high-quality changes in the management system of the institution.

Time Management - Literally translated - "time", "control" or control of time, but in reality no one can control time, because it is not a material dimension.

A more correct and correct semantic translation is "organization of time". If we go deeper into this concept, it is a technology for organizing and improving the efficiency of using time to achieve any goal, a technology for effective planning of work and personal time.

In a broad sense, "time management is a set of laws, rules, methods, strategies aimed at achieving results - effective use of time, as follows:

- organization: making lists and setting priorities among team members, distributing and handing over responsibilities;
- monitoring, quality of implementation of work plan, assessment of intended and achieved goals based on criteria;
- correction, changes, additions, clarifications to current plans, according to the scheme: 1-day plan several times, 1-month plan - every week, for a quarter - once a month, plan for 1 year - 2 times; In addition, an analysis of the time spent on tasks is performed.

The fifth point is an important addition, without which it is impossible to implement the next stage of the activity system - it is necessary to find resources (financial, personnel, time) to implement the planned actions.

The main goal of the preschool educational organization is to form the necessary life competence and achieve the level of development in accordance with the state standards in the graduate of the preschool educational organization.

It can be considered as a general plan for the implementation of the tasks set in the state educational standard. The Long-Term Intermediate Plan is a state education standard for K-12, a state requirement, and the First Step curriculum. The next step includes original and customized child development programs and innovative projects for a period of 1 to 3 years.

Analogues of medium-term, intermediate and short-term plans include partial, customized, work programs, annual work plan of the organization, long-term and calendar work planning.

Time management technology includes various planning tools. We use some of them every day. Often, when planning our work, we keep diaries that list the most important tasks or meetings that we need to remember.

When planning your time management, it is recommended to use spreadsheets, which are a good tool to evenly distribute the workload and tick boxes on time.

For medium-term planning, we use a schedule divided into 12 months, which helps to evenly distribute the load for each month and see the implementation of planned activities.

"The only thieves in our society who go unpunished are the thieves of time," said Napoleon Bonaparte.

To solve completed problems, you need to set priorities (in terms of importance and urgency of implementation), consider the possibility of delegating planned tasks, that is, properly plan your activities.

Now you may be thinking about the question: do I personally need time management? Thinking about the possible outcomes of using time management technology can help us answer that.

In conclusion, if we inculcate "valuing and saving time" into the future citizens of our country from a young age, they will always overcome problems and obstacles during their life with patience and perseverance.

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